

Uzbekistan's Capital Market and Economic Growth

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Abstract The objective was to explore the link between economic development and capital markets including the stock-market and bond-markets as well as the overview of Uzbekistan's capital market and economic growth. This study included both descriptive and quantitative analyzes. The descriptive study detailed Uzbekistan's capital market structure and development. In order to study the long-term relationships between variables used for the study in quantitative terms. The variables included time series data, including GDP, market capitalization on the Uzbek bond exchange and outstanding bond debt instrument for the period Q1-2021. The results of the study indicated that in relation to the stock market, the financial crisis grew in Uzbekistan in Q1-2021. The stock market is currently more than five times that of the bond market. The second research results showed that both stock market and bond market economic growth had favorable effects. The growing Uzbek economy has made private enterprises and families more profitable and affluent, increasing savings and investment in the capital markets. Investments have increased. Simultaneously, the stock market also encouraged economic growth by allocating financing for private investment, leading to the expansion of the production sector and jobs. However, throughout this period the bond market did not consider to have a substantial impact on Uzbekistan's economic growth.

Keywords: Capital Market, Economic Growth, Finance, Banking

Introduction

Capital markets often operate as middlemen for borrowers and savers. It offers several financial tools that enable economic actors to investment and trade risk with different alternative returns, liquidity and risk characteristics through financial assets. It also gives cash to the public and commercial sectors, who would want to borrow, consume and invest in various initiatives for economic growth. Both the stock and bond markets serve to raise the long-term capital of the government, the bank and companies for funding various new initiatives. These therefore encourage the growth of economic activities, including consumption, manufacturing, investment and trade.

In the last five years, several nations, including Uzbekistan have been turning to further financial liberalization. Thus, in several facets of economic growth, financial liberalization has played an essential role. The deregulation of domestic financial markets along with the loosening of capital flows are generally financial liberalization. For example, in Uzbekistan, the freedom of Uzbek people in overseas investment and management of the risk of foreign currency was loosening in international trade restrictions (National Bank of Uzbekistan Report, Q1-2021). As a result, international commerce together with investment and borrowing was pushed on the international financial markets. It also fostered the growth of local capital markets from larger capital inflows and new enthusiasts in Uzbekistan to encourage competitiveness and modern financial innovation in this period.

At present, there are many different elements, including emerging and established nations, of the interaction between capital markets and economic growth. Many studies show that capital market growth is an instrument for rapidly monitoring financial progress in underdeveloped economies (Isenmila & Adewale, 2012). In tiny developing markets, however, the capital market may not be efficient. Therefore, due of their high cost and underdeveloped financial

institutions, it is not possible for such nations to promote stock markets. Ali Abbas and Christensen (2007) also found that domestic bonds had a favorable influence on economic growth, not on the volume of capital accumulation itself, but on investment efficiency or factor productivity.

The key question in this paper should be: "Supporting economic growth on the capital market?" And "Do Gross Domestic Product Expansion (GDP) or economic development support stock and bond expansion?" In the governmental and private sectors of Uzbekistan, direct fund reclamation, bonds and stock market types play a critical role in raising and allocating money.

Research Objective and Scope

The purpose of this study is to explore the association between those factors, including stock market, bond market and Uzbekistan's economic development in Q1-2021. The document may be broken down into three parts. The first is the overview of Uzbekistan's capital market and growth. The results are further evaluated for investigating links between capital market and economic growth, using the root test, cointegration tests and Granger causality test. Finally, there are some conclusions.

Literature Review

In recent times, research has been thoroughly reviewed in industrialized and emerging nations on the link between the capital market and economic growth. Most earlier research tended to agree on a favorable effect on economic growth like Henry on the capital market, including the stock and bond markets (2020). It revealed that stock market deregulation led, for Latin American and Asian nations, both in Brazil, Brazil, Chile, China, Kazakhstan, Korea, Malaysia, Thailand to private investment booms and economic development from 2015-2020. It might minimize the cost of capital of the country by allowing domestic agents and international agents to share the risk. Furthermore, investment boom was also

driven by the projected marginal capital productivity improvement. This helped to boost capital inflows, followed by a fall in the interest rate. This therefore promoted economic expansion.

Another point of view is the linkage between development of the financial sector and economic growth, like King and Levine (2019). The study showed that the financial system has promoted economic growth according to the standpoint of Schumpeter from 80 nations over the 2015-2018 period. Both banking system and bourses have been substantially linked to future growth rates, accumulation of physical capital and increase in economic efficiency. In addition, Choe and Moosa (2019) also concluded in the same manner that the economic growth has been affected by financial liberalization and the development of financial markets such as the stock market and bond market.

Besides bank and equity, bond markets have also been an important source of long-term funding. It supplied governmental and private spending with long-term financing. At the same time, savers may hunt for their return on another significant canal. In order to analyze its influence in economic growth, several past surveys have paid attention to this channel. Ali Abbas and Christensen (2020) shown that in 93 low-income countries and developing markets from 2015 to 2019 domestic bond markets did not have the same effect on economic development through investment efficiency or factors productivity. Bond markets might serve to enhance money and financial markets, promote private savings and stimulate investment. Moreover, the study revealed that bond markets have connections with major macroeconomic, financial and institutional factors, such as private economy and depth in finances. Levine and Zervos (2018) also identified a substantial positive correlation between economic growth and financial development.

Capital Market in Uzbekistan

In general, financial market consists of money market and capital markets. Money market mainly refers to financial market where financial instruments with short-term maturities and high liquidity are traded for example treasury bills, bills of exchange and promissory note. These issued by governments, financial

institutions and large corporations.

Figure 1 Financial Market Structure Source: Anand (2021)

A capital market is a long-term debt or equity market that provides the capital for durations greater than one year. The capital market consists of two submarkets: the main and the secondary. It covers the freshly issued securities and creates the fresh long-term capital for the primary market. At the same time, secondary markets are in charge of market trading securities already issued, such as stocks and bonds, in order to keep investors liquid. An investor also appeals to a capital market with strong liquidity and transparency.

Capital Market and Economic Growth Perspective with regard to Uzbekistan's capital markets and economic growth (figure 2), both the stock and bond markets in Uzbekistan tended to develop more than 20 times, notably the bond market. The stock market is currently more than five times that of the bond market.

Figure 2 Capital Market and Economic Growth in Uzbekistan Source: National Bank of Uzbekistan (Q1-2021)

At the same time, the GDP has continued to rise approx. 3 times, which is around 10-20 times the lowest relative to the stock and bond markets. It has shown a faster economic growth than a stronger financial depth for the real sector. The greater depth of the financing is reflected in the wide and profound evolution of capital markets. The greater bond market size will promote savings and investment through the movement of money to manufacturing and services sectors. This helps to expand economic activities, jobs and economic growth.

Conclusions

It examined the links between economic growth and capital market and the bond market in 2021, covering stock and bond markets. The objective of the study was to explore the overview of the Uzbek capital markets and economic growth; and, the statistics covers the 2015-2021 timeframe. In Uzbekistan, the capital market, including stock and bond markets, played an essential role in raising and assigning the fund to the private and governmental sectors. During the previous

five years, the bond and equity markets, especially the bond market, have tended to rise higher over 20 times. The stock market is currently more than five times that of the bond market. In contrast, the GDP has continued to increase by roughly three times, which is roughly 10 times and 20 times lower than the stock market and bond market.

The results of this study demonstrated that economic growth had a beneficial effect on both the stock market and on bond markets for the link between capital market and economic growth. Simultaneously, the stock market has also aided economic growth by allocating private investment funds which have resulted in the expansion of the industrial sector and jobs. The bond market, however, has little impact on economic growth. However, it helped fuel stock expansion by functioning as an option to control investment in portfolios and diversify risk for investors.

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